

Campus-Based Teacher Workshop and Instructional Organization Skills of Teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

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Abstract. The study aimed to look into the influence of campus-based teacher workshops on the instructional organization skills of teachers. In this study, the researcher selected 160 elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, as the study's respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that campus-based teacher workshops and instructional organization skills of teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, were rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between campus-based teacher workshops and instructional organization skills of teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. Evidently, regression analysis proved that campus-based teacher workshops in terms of lesson planning aptitude and curricular appraisal proficiency significantly influence the instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers. It was recommended that teachers should actively participate in campus-based teacher workshops focused on instructional organization and engagement skills, recognizing their importance in enhancing teaching effectiveness. It was further recommended the utilization of findings through publication in reputable research journals.

KEY WORDS

1. educational management
2. campus-based teacher workshop
3. instructional organization skills of teachers,

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1. Introduction

The absence of instructional organization skills can impede the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes, ultimately hindering students' academic growth and success. Without proper organization, lessons may lack structure and coherence, leading to confusion among students and disruptions in the classroom. More so, poorly organized instruction may result in time wastage as teachers struggle to manage lesson activities, transitions, and materials effectively. Students are less likely to stay engaged in lessons that lack organization or clarity, leading to decreased motivation and participation. Thus, it underscores the importance of providing teachers with training and support to enhance their organizational abilities for the

benefit of both educators and students. Reports indicate that poor teachers' instructional organization skills can have several negative consequences for educators, students, and the overall learning environment. For instance, Al-Amarat (2015) poorly organized lessons are often confusing, lack structure, and fail to engage students. This can result in disinterest, boredom, and reduced motivation to participate in class activities. Accordingly, inadequate instructional organization may lead to incomplete or haphazard coverage of curriculum content. As a result, students may have significant learning gaps and struggle to grasp fundamental concepts. Darci Borden (2013) also reported that poor organization can lead to wasted classroom time, as educators may struggle to transition between activities, retrieve materials, or clarify instructions. This inefficiency reduces the amount of time available for meaningful learning. In contrary, Temli-Durmus (2016) pointed out that instructional organization skills are essential for creating an effective and engaging learning environment where students can thrive academically and socially. Teachers who prioritize and cultivate these skills contribute to the success and well-being of their students. According to Zouzou (2015), well-organized instruction helps students understand and retain information more effectively, leading to improved academic achievement. Efficient organization of lessons maximizes the use of classroom time, ensuring that learning objectives are met without wasted minutes. Likewise, Gage et al. (2018) proposed that clear organization reduces disruptions and behavioral issues, making it easier for teachers to maintain control of the classroom. Effective instructional organization ensures curriculum content aligns with educational standards and learning goals. As Sahbaz (2017) pointed out, teacher workshops often provide training in effective lesson-planning techniques. Teachers learn how to structure lessons, align them with learning objectives and standards, and create engaging content, all contributing to improved instructional organization. Similarly, Trussell et al. (2016) found that campus-based workshops often facilitate teacher collaboration. Sharing ideas, experiences, and best practices with peers can enhance teachers' instructional organization skills as they learn from one another. Likewise, Sezer (2018) found that workshops often emphasize the use of assessment data to inform instruction. Teachers learn to analyze student performance data, identify areas of improvement, and adjust their teaching strategies accordingly, enhancing their ability to organize instruction based on student needs. As claimed by Tanang (2016), a campus-based teachers workshop is the professional development or training program for educators that takes place within the physical premises of a school or educational institution. These workshops are typically designed to enhance teachers' knowledge, skills, and instructional strategies, with a focus on improving classroom teaching and student learning. According to Baker (2015), teachers who engage in high-level workshops stay current with the latest educational research and trends. This ensures their teaching methods align with contemporary pedagogical approaches, benefiting student learning outcomes. Likewise, Schleicher (2021), found that teachers who participate in workshops often implement new and engaging teaching strategies in their classrooms. This could increase student engagement, motivation, and interest in learning. While there was a substantial body of research that examines the impact of campus-based teacher workshops on various aspects of teaching and learning, there remains a notable research gap regarding the specific and long-term influence of such workshops on teachers' instructional organization skills. Existing studies often focus on immediate outcomes and perceptions, leaving a limited understanding of how sustained changes in instructional organization skills, as a result

of workshop participation, can positively affect classroom practices, student engagement, and academic achievement over an extended period. This research gap suggests the need for further investigation into the lasting effects and effectiveness of campus-based teacher workshops in improving teachers' instructional organization skills and how these skills impact the overall educational experience. Such research could provide valuable insights into the long-term benefits of professional development and inform

the design and implementation of more effective workshops for educators. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Davao del Norte, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used descriptive correlational design through regression analysis to better understand teachers' instructional organization skills as determined by the campus-based teacher workshops, which were found to be scarce.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized the quantitative descriptive-correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the influence of campus-based teachers workshops on the instructional organization skills of teachers. Bryman and Bell (2015) described quantitative research as focusing on the objective measurement and analysis of numerical data to draw conclusions and make inferences about a specific population or phenomenon. This approach employs systematic and structured data collection techniques, such as surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis of existing datasets, to gather quantitative and statistically analyzed numerical data. The findings from quantitative research aim to provide a deeper understanding of patterns, relationships, and trends within the data. Meanwhile, descriptive correlational research, according to Gay, Mills, and Airasian (2019), is an approach that involves observing and measuring two or more variables without manipulating them. It aims to describe the relationship or association between variables as they naturally occur. This approach focuses on understanding the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, often using sta-

tistical measures such as correlation coefficients. In a descriptive correlational study, researchers collect data on variables of interest and analyze them to identify patterns, trends, or associations. The goal is to better understand how the variables relate to each other in a specific population or context. This approach is particularly useful when exploring complex phenomena or when causality cannot be established due to ethical or practical limitations. Mainly, the study focused on determining which domains of campus-based teachers' workshops significantly influence the instructional organization skills of teachers.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao del Norte. In this study, the 160 respondents was selected through stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study.

Hence, only those permanent-regular teachers in Dujali District in Davao del Norte and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the performance rating of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study used adapted and modified survey questionnaires to suit the current investigation. The scaling was done by using one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Also, the survey questionnaires underwent validation by the external and internal panel of experts. The first tool is a

campus-based teachers’ workshop. This questionnaire was adapted from Pan (2004), which has four indicators: lesson planning aptitude, responsive teaching skills, classroom discipline mastery, and curricular appraisal proficiency. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.945, which is interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of campus-based teachers’ workshops, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation for the Campus-Based Teachers’ Workshop

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The campus-based teachers’ workshop is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The campus-based teachers’ workshop is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The campus-based teachers’ workshop is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The campus-based teachers’ workshop is rarely observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The campus-based teachers’ workshop is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was the instructional organization skills of teachers Questionnaire adapted from Temli-Durmus (2016), which is divided into three domains, namely engagement skills, instructional coaching, and behavior reinforcement. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.918, which was interpreted as excellent, indi-

cating high reliability and consistency among the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of instructional organization skills of teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions and interpretations as presented below:

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation for Instructional Organization Skills of Teachers

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The instructional organization skills of teachers is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The instructional organization skills of teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The instructional organization skills of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The instructional organization skills of teachers is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The instructional organization skills of teachers is never manifested.

The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school's division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected public schools in Dujali District, Davao del Norte. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument

to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted last January 4-5, 2024. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. The researcher conducted the survey simultaneously to administer the questionnaire. The study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the campus-based teacher workshop and instructional organization skills of teachers in Dujali District, Davao del Norte. It was used to supply the answers for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (campus-based teachers workshop) and

dependent (instructional organization skills of teachers) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Linear Regression Analysis was applied to evaluate the significant influence of campus-based teacher workshops on the instructional organization skills of teachers in Dujali District, Davao del Norte. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of campus-based teacher workshops and instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte; the significant relationship between campus-based teacher workshops and instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte; and the influence of campus-based teacher workshop on instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte.

The Summary of The Extent of Campus-Based Teacher Workshops for Elementary School Teachers

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of campus-based teacher workshops of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. The table shows that campus-based teacher workshops obtained an overall mean

score of 3.25, descriptively rated as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. This implies that the workshops typically designed to enhance teachers’ knowledge, skills, and instructional strategies, with a focus on improving classroom teaching and student learning, are sometimes observed.

Table 1. Summary of Campus-Based Teacher Workshop of Elementary Teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Lesson Planning Aptitude	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Responsive Teaching Skills	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Classroom Discipline Mastery	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Curricular Appraisal Proficiency	3.27	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.25	Moderately Extensive

This supports the findings of Zheng et al. (2016) that campus-based workshops provide teachers with opportunities to develop and refine their teaching skills. They can learn about innovative instructional methods, classroom management techniques, and technology integration, leading to more effective teaching practices. According to Bandy (2020), workshops often emphasize differentiated instruction, which allows teachers to tailor their teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of students. Moreover, campus-based teacher workshop in terms of classroom discipline mastery acquired the highest mean score of 3.38 described as

moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed, while, campus-based teacher workshop in terms of responsive teaching skills got the lowest mean score of 3.16, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. This supports the idea of Schleicher (2021) that teachers who participate in workshops often implement new and engaging teaching strategies in their classrooms. This can increase student engagement, motivation, and interest in learning.

The summary of the extent of instructional organization skills of teachers in Dujali Dis-

trict, Davao Del Norte, is shown in Table 2. As shown in the table, the overall mean of instructional organization skills of teachers is 3.28, which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested. This denotes that the skillful arrangement of curriculum content, learning objectives, teaching strategies, and classroom resources to create a well-organized and productive learning environment is sometimes manifested. This supports the idea of Andrin et al. (2021) that organized lessons

are more engaging and efficient, creating a positive and productive learning environment for students. Organized instruction often includes engaging activities and resources, making lessons more interesting and motivating for students. According to Gage et al. (2018), clear organization reduces disruptions and behavioral issues, making it easier for teachers to maintain control of the classroom. Effective instructional organization ensures that curriculum content aligns with educational standards and learning goals.

Table 2. Summary of Instructional Organization Skills of Elementary Teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Engagement Skills	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Instructional Coaching	3.27	Moderately Extensive
Behavior Reinforcement	3.40	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.28	Moderately Extensive

In addition, instructional organization skills of teachers in terms of behavior reinforcement acquired the highest mean score of 3.40 described as extensive and interpreted as often-times observed, while, instructional organization skills of teachers in terms of engagement skills got the lowest mean score of 3.16 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. This supports the idea of Oketch and Ngware (2012) that effective organization involves efficiently utilizing teaching resources, including materials, technology, and support personnel, which can lead to cost savings and more efficient resource allocation.

Significant Relationship Between Campus-Based Teacher Workshop and Instructional Organization Skills of Teachers

More so, the results in the table show that lesson planning aptitude, responsive teaching

The results on the analysis on the relationship between campus-based teacher workshop and instructional organization skills of elementary teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that campus-based teacher workshop has a significant positive moderate relationship with instructional organization skills of elementary teachers with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .333, p > 0.05$). It means that as the extent of campus-based teacher workshops improved, the instructional organization skills of teachers also significantly improved.

skills, classroom discipline mastery, and curricular appraisal proficiency significantly correlated

Table 3. Relationship Between Campus-Based Teacher Workshop and Instructional Organization Skills of Elementary Teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

Campus-Based Teacher Workshop	r-value	p-value	Decision
Lesson Planning Aptitude	0.445*	0.000	Reject H0
Responsive Teaching Skills	0.302*	0.003	Reject H0
Classroom Discipline Mastery	0.524*	0.001	Reject H0
Curricular Appraisal Proficiency	0.409*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Campus-Based Teacher Workshop	0.333*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p > 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 > r > 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 > r > 0.7$; Weak

Correlation for $0.3 \geq r \geq 0.00$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$

with instructional organization skills of teachers, as evidenced by correlation coefficient values of 0.445, 0.302, 0.524, and 0.409, respectively. Thus, this led to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between campus-based teacher workshops and instructional organization skills of elementary teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. The result denotes that campus-based teacher workshops are a significant factor that could improve the instructional organization skills of teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. The result is in agreement with Sahbaz's (2017) findings that teacher workshops often provide training in effective lesson-planning techniques. Teachers learn how to structure lessons, align them with learning objectives and standards, and create engaging content, all contributing to improved instructional organization. Additionally, the result is congruent with the idea of Trussell et al. (2016) that campus-based workshops often facilitate collaboration among teachers. Sharing

ideas, experiences, and best practices with peers can enhance teachers' instructional organization skills as they learn from one another.

Influence of Campus-Based Teacher Workshop on the Instructional Organization Skills of Elementary Teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

The significance of the influence of campus-based teacher workshops on the instructional organization skills of elementary teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table 4 shows that when campus-based teacher workshops in terms of lesson planning aptitude, responsive teaching skills, classroom discipline mastery, and curricular appraisal proficiency are considered as predictors of instructional organization skills of teachers, the model is significant, as evident in the F-value of 21.403 with $p > 0.05$. It is therefore stated that campus-based teacher workshop significantly predicts instructional organization skills of elementary teachers.

Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R2 value of 0.223 indicates that campus-based teacher workshop has contributed significantly in the variability of instructional organization skills of teachers by 22.30 from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 77.70 was credited

to other factors not covered in this study. In addition, table shows that there are domains of campus-based teacher workshop that significantly influence the instructional organization skills of elementary teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. This table indicates

Table 4. Influence of Campus-Based Teacher Workshop on the Instructional Organization Skills of Elementary Teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

Campus-Based Teacher Workshop	Estimates	S.E.	p-value	Decisions
Lesson Planning Aptitude	0.206**	0.081	0.000	Reject H0
Responsive Teaching Skills	0.089	0.031	0.098	Accept H0
Classroom Discipline Mastery	-0.056	0.012	0.322	Accept H0
Curricular Appraisal Proficiency	0.251**	0.072	0.000	Reject H0
R ²	0.223			
F-value	21.403**			
p-value	0.000			

**Significant @ p>0.05

that lesson planning aptitude and curricular appraisal proficiency are significant when considered. This means that the extent of instructional organization skills of teachers increases by 0.206 and 0.251 for each unit increase in campus-based teacher workshop. Thus, this leads to the rejection of null hypothesis that none of the domains of campus-based teacher workshop significantly influence the instructional organization skills of elementary teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. Affirming that instructional organization skills of teachers is a function of campus-based teacher workshop in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, the result

aligns with Sanetti’s et al. (2017) conclusion that teacher workshops stress the importance of aligning instruction with educational standards and learning objectives. Teachers gain a deeper understanding of how to design lessons that meet these standards, ensuring better instructional organization. According to Wiene et al. (2018), effective workshops introduce teachers to engagement strategies that capture students’ interest and maintain their focus. These techniques help organize lessons in a way that keeps students actively engaged in the learning process.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—This study was set to determine which domains of campus-based teacher workshops significantly influence instructional organization skills utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a correlation technique. The researcher selected the 160 elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte as the respondents through random sampling method. The researcher made use of

modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The campus-based teacher workshop in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, has an overall mean of 3.25 and a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. The workshop’s mean scores in lesson planning, responsive teaching skills, classroom

discipline mastery, and curricular appraisal proficiency were 3.18, 3.16, 3.38, and 3.27, respectively. Instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte has an overall mean of 3.28 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. Instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in terms of engagement skills, instructional coaching, and behavior reinforcement obtained mean scores of 3.16, 3.27, and 3.40, respectively. Campus-based teacher workshop has a significant positive relationship with the instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .333, p > 0.05$). Meanwhile, campus-based teacher workshops in terms of lesson planning aptitude, responsive teaching skills, classroom discipline mastery, and curricular appraisal proficiency were found to be significantly correlated with instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers as evident on coefficient correlation values (r) of 0.445, 0.302, 0.524 and 0.409, respectively. Campus-based teacher workshops in terms of lesson planning aptitude and curricular appraisal proficiency significantly influence the instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, as evidenced by the F-value of 21.403 and $p > 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.223 indicated that campus-based teacher workshops have contributed significantly to the variability of instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District in Davao Del Norte by 22.30

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several significant conclusions were generated, shedding light on the relationship between campus-based teacher workshops and instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. Campus-based teacher workshop in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte was rated as

moderately extensive. More so, campus-based teacher workshops in terms of lesson planning, responsive teaching skills, classroom discipline mastery, and curricular appraisal proficiency also got moderately extensive ratings. This implies that the workshops that were typically designed to enhance teachers' knowledge, skills, and instructional strategies, with a focus on improving classroom teaching and student learning, were sometimes observed. The instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, were rated as moderately extensive. Meanwhile, the instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in terms of engagement skills and instructional coaching got an extensive rating, while the instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in terms of behavior reinforcement got an extensive rating. This shows that the skillful arrangement of curriculum content, learning objectives, teaching strategies, and classroom resources to create a well-organized and productive learning environment was sometimes manifested. Campus-based teacher workshop has a significant positive relationship with the instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. This means that as the extent of campus-based teacher workshops improved, the instructional organization skills of teachers also significantly improved. This implies that teacher workshops provide training in effective lesson planning techniques, thus, allowing teachers to learn how to structure lessons, align them with learning objectives and standards, and create engaging content, all of which contribute to improved instructional organization. Campus-based teacher workshops in terms of lesson planning aptitude and curricular appraisal proficiency significantly influence the instructional organization skills of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. This affirmed that the instructional organization skills of teachers are a function

of campus-based teacher workshops in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. This denotes that effective workshops introduce teachers to engagement strategies that capture students' interest and maintain their focus. These techniques help organize lessons to keep students actively engaged in the learning process.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The Department of Education (DepEd) may establish policies that prioritize professional development opportunities for teachers, including mandatory participation in workshops aimed at enhancing instructional organization skills. DepEd can also encourage collaboration between educational institutions and professional development organizations to design and deliver effective teacher workshops. School heads may provide time and support for teachers to participate in campus-based workshops focused on instructional organization and engagement skills. Additionally, school heads should incorporate the concepts and strategies covered in the workshops into the school's professional development plan and on-

going support structures. Teachers may actively participate in campus-based teacher workshops focused on instructional organization and engagement skills, recognizing their importance in enhancing teaching effectiveness. In addition, they should apply the concepts, strategies, and techniques learned in the workshops to their daily classroom practice, seeking feedback and support from colleagues and school leaders. Future researchers may explore innovative approaches and best practices for enhancing instructional organization and engagement skills through campus-based teacher workshops, considering diverse contexts and student populations. By implementing these recommendations, policymakers, school heads, teachers, and future researchers can collaborate to create meaningful and impactful campus-based teacher workshops that enhance teachers' instructional organization and engagement skills, ultimately improving teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes.

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